

HOMOGENIZED PARAMETERS OF THE FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO THE STOCHASTIC AGING PROCESSES

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SUMMARY

The main aim of this paper is to present an application of the generalized stochastic perturbation technique to model the stochastic aging processes of the fibre-reinforced periodic composite materials in terms of their effective properties. The perturbation technique is used here in its Response Function Method to detect for various time moments of the aging process the analytical interrelations between the effective elasticity tensor components and the composite parameters exposed to the aging phenomena. Numerical procedure based on the FEM code MCCEFF and the system MAPLE is used here to model aging of the glass-epoxy composites and may find a general application in the reliability analysis of various composite structures.

Keywords: fibre-reinforced composites, homogenisation method, stochastic ageing, Finite Element Method, Monte-Carlo simulation

1. INTRODUCTION

A computational modeling of the stochastic processes [5] based on the Monte-Carlo simulation method is known for their large time consumption because the entire generalizations of random populations in different discrete time moments are evaluated and used in various Finite Element Method models. More optimal strategy would be based on the observation of the probabilistic moments of the examined processes in the same time moments as before performed with at least the comparable accuracy. The generalized stochastic perturbation technique based on the Taylor expansion of the uncertain parameters and the state functions may be useful in this case, to determine for instance the probabilistic moments of the effective elasticity tensor. However, we need to have the analytical description for the basic moments of the stochastic process(es) being modeled to assure the sufficient input for the perturbation-based analysis. This process does not need to have the Gaussian realizations for the whole history, however the lack of correlation between various parameters simplifies significantly the analysis. Contrary to the second order second moment implementations of the perturbation technique, the hierarchical equations are not solved for the increasing order approximants for the probabilistic output. Now, the Response Function Method (RFM)

is explored, where the polynomial interrelation between the stochastic output and input is to be approximated symbolically via several deterministic solutions around the mean values of the stochastic parameters in various time moments of the process. Finally, one can obtain a discrete polynomial approximation of the stochastic process as the function of the initial stochastic process of the aging, for instance. Thanks to such an approach, the classical Finite Element Method programs (with and without the access to the solver source code) may be employed.

The engineering practice in composites (and even classical homogeneous engineering materials) shows that the aging of materials (neglecting the real nature of this mechanism) is dangerous for many structures and elements and should be included into the designing process. An integral part of such a designing process should be mathematical equation simulating the aging behavior of various structural elements and materials, a proper computational modeling technique as well as the final conclusion stating the safe time of operation for the specific engineering structure in the given environment. The mathematical equation responsible for the aging process may be proposed using the strength verification, however it would need the very large number of experimentation extended for the very long periods of time. Instead of it one may adopt some aging model proposed extensively in the literature and following the research made in various applied science and engineering branches – like exponential or linear aging decay for different physical or mechanical parameters [1].

Taking into account the above considerations the stochastic aging laws applied for the Young moduli of the composite components and, separately, for the fiber radius are examined in terms of the effective parameters for the periodic fiber-reinforced. The linear decay responsible for the aging process is adopted, where the initial value and the aging velocity are the Gaussian random parameters constant in time [4]. Thanks to this definition of the stochastic process it is possible to determine the basic probabilistic moments for the considered parameters and to include them into the homogenization procedure. In turn, this procedure is based on the Finite Element Method program MCCEFF determining the homogenized stochastic elasticity tensor in plain strain (for the rectangular periodicity cell and the fiber embedded into it) using the generalized stochastic perturbation technique [2,3]. Some additional algebraic computations are completed in the system MAPLE (interoperating with the program MCCEFF), where the response functions are found and used to determine finally stochastic processes [5] and where all graphical representations for the stochastic processes are provided. Let us underline that the comparison of the tenth order perturbation approach with the Monte-Carlo simulation results were proven before in various computational experiments with random variables, so that it was employed here to discuss the interrelations between the mechanical parameters and the fiber radius aging with the time variations of the probabilistic moments for the composite effective parameters.

2. FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITE MODEL

The periodic fiber-reinforced composite structure in the plane strain with linear elastic and transversely isotropic components and some stochastic parameters is considered now. Let us denote the Representative Volume Element (RVE) of this composite as Ω ;

$Y \subset \mathfrak{R}^2$ stands for the section of this composite with $x_3 = 0$ plane being constant along the x_3 axis parallel to the fibers direction.

Figure 1. Periodic fiber reinforced composite

Let the region Ω contain two perfectly bonded, coherent and disjoint subsets Ω_1 (fiber) and Ω_2 (matrix) and let the scale between corresponding geometrical diameters of Ω and Y is described by some small and real parameter $\varepsilon > 0$. Let $\partial\Omega$ denote external boundary of the Ω while $\partial\Omega_{12}$ - the interface boundary between Ω_1 and Ω_2 regions. The elasticity coefficients are defined here as

$$C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{x}) = A_{ijkl}(\mathbf{x}) e(\mathbf{x}) = e(\mathbf{x}) \left\{ \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} \frac{\nu(\mathbf{x})}{(1+\nu(\mathbf{x}))(1-2\nu(\mathbf{x}))} + (\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{jk}) \frac{1}{2(1+\nu(\mathbf{x}))} \right\} \quad (1)$$

The effective tensor $C_{ijkl}^{(\text{eff})}$ (for the artificial homogenized composite) is introduced as such a tensor that replacing C_{ijkl}^ε (for the real composite) with $C_{ijkl}^{(\text{eff})}$ in the following equilibrium equations:

$$C_{ijkl}^\varepsilon \varepsilon_{kl}(\mathbf{u}^\varepsilon) + f_i = 0; \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(\mathbf{u}^\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{u}_{i,j}^\varepsilon + \mathbf{u}_{j,i}^\varepsilon); \mathbf{x} \in \Omega \quad (3)$$

$$C_{ijkl}^\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}) = \chi_1(\mathbf{x}) C_{ijkl}^{(1)} + (1 - \chi_1(\mathbf{x})) C_{ijkl}^{(2)} \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{u}^0 is obtained as a solution being a weak limit of \mathbf{u}^ε with $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and where the characteristic function defining the elastic parameters equals to

$$\chi_1(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_1 \\ 0, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_2 \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$\mathbf{u}^\varepsilon = 0; \mathbf{x} \in \partial\Omega. \quad (6)$$

Now, let us consider the stochastic variations in Young modulus within the composite, i.e.

$$C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{x}; \omega; t) = A_{ijkl}(\mathbf{x}) e(\mathbf{x}; \omega; t), \quad (7)$$

with the following representation [4]:

$$e(\mathbf{x}; \omega; t) = -\dot{e}(\mathbf{x}; \omega)t + e^0(\mathbf{x}; \omega). \quad (8)$$

The random field $e^0(\mathbf{x}; \omega)$ is equivalent to the initial Young moduli of the composite constituents, whereas $\dot{e}(\mathbf{x}; \omega)$ represents the velocity of ageing process for the matrix and the fibre separately, i.e.

$$\dot{e}(\mathbf{x}; \omega) = \psi_1(\mathbf{x}) \dot{e}_1(\omega) + (1 - \psi_1(\mathbf{x})) \dot{e}_2(\omega). \quad (9)$$

It is assumed that this process is of course continuous in time and the particular components are fully uncorrelated from each other (Young modulus of both components and the fiber radius). Taking into account the relation (5) one can write that

$$E[\dot{e}(x; \omega)] = \chi_1 E[\dot{e}_1] + (1 - \chi_1) E[\dot{e}_2] \text{ for } \chi_1 = \begin{cases} 1; & x \in \Omega_1 \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases}; \quad (10)$$

the variance is defined accordingly as

$$\text{Var}(\dot{e}(x; \omega)) = \chi_1 \text{Var}(\dot{e}_1) + (1 - \chi_1) \text{Var}(\dot{e}_2); \quad (11)$$

Quite analogous relations hold true for the initial random distribution of the components Young moduli. Further, it is also assumed that some geometrical parameters may be subjected to the stochastic aging driven decay; one of the most influential case would be the fibre radius, so that we define accordingly

$$R(\mathbf{x}; \omega; t) = -\dot{R}(\mathbf{x}; \omega)t + R^0(\mathbf{x}; \omega). \quad (12)$$

Then, the effective elasticity tensor definition

$$C_{ijkl}^{(eff)}(\omega; t) = \langle C_{ijkl}(x; \omega; t) \rangle_{\Omega} + \langle \sigma_{ij}^{(kl)}(x; \omega; t) \rangle_{\Omega}. \quad (13)$$

It includes the integration over the stochastically varying fiber region unlike the case with the stochastic Young modulus only.

3. PERTURBATION-BASED STOCHASTIC ANALYSIS

Let us introduce the random variable $b(\omega)$ and its probability density function as $p(b)$ as the representation of the considered stochastic process at the given time t and let us expand all the input variables and all the state functions of the given problem via Taylor series about their spatial expectations using some small real perturbation parameter like

for the random function $f(b)$

$$f = f^0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \varepsilon^n \frac{\partial^n f}{\partial b^n} (\Delta b)^n, \quad (14)$$

where

$$\varepsilon \Delta b = \varepsilon (b - b^0) \quad (15)$$

is the first variation of b about its expected value. Symbol $(.)^0$ represents the function value $(.)$ taken at the expectation b^0 . The expected values of this function is derived as

$$\begin{aligned} E[f(b)] &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(b) p(b) db = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(f^0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \varepsilon^n \frac{\partial^n f}{\partial b^n} \Delta b^n \right) p(b) db = \\ &= f^0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon^n}{n!} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\partial^n f}{\partial b^n} \Delta b^n p(b) db \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

This power expansion is valid only if the state function $f(b)$ is analytic with respect to ε and the Taylor series converge; usually this parameter is taken as equal to 1 in numerous practical computations. Therefore, now this quantity ε is treated as the expansion parameter and is included explicitly in all the further derivations including analytical expressions. Numerical studies performed in the next section demonstrate the influence of this parameter on basic probabilistic moments and characteristics in various orders of the perturbation methodology – all the moments are obtained in the form of polynomials of the additional order with respect to ε . Thanks to such an extension of the random output, any desired efficiency of the expected values as well as higher probabilistic moments can be achieved by an appropriate choice of the parameters m and ε corresponding to the input probability density function (PDF) type, relations between the probabilistic moments, acceptable error of the computations etc. Analogously, it is possible to derive the formulas describing higher order moments, especially in all those cases, where m is given. The recursive formula for the central α th order probabilistic moment in 10th order approximation can be determined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_m(f(b)) &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(f^0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\varepsilon^i}{i!} \Delta b^i \frac{\partial^i f}{\partial b^i} - E[f(b)] \right)^m p(b) db = \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(f^0(b) + f^{,b} \varepsilon \Delta b + f^{,bb} \varepsilon^2 \frac{(\Delta b)^2}{2!} \dots \frac{\partial^{10} f(b)}{\partial b^{10}} \varepsilon^{10} \frac{(\Delta b)^{10}}{10!} - E[f(b)] \right)^m p(b) db = \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(f^{,b} \varepsilon \Delta b + f^{,bb} \varepsilon^2 \frac{(\Delta b)^2}{2!} \dots \frac{\partial^{10} f(b)}{\partial b^{10}} \varepsilon^{10} \frac{(\Delta b)^{10}}{10!} \right)^m p(b) db \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

As one may see, the crucial part of the perturbation-based approach is a determination of the partial derivatives of the output function with respect to the input random (or stochastic) parameter(s). As far as the relation between those two quantities remains

unknown (since no analytical solution available) one may construct the polynomial approximation of the homogenized tensor $C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(eff)}$ with respect to b in the following form:

$$C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(eff)} = A_1^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^{n-1} + A_2^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^{n-2} + \dots + A_n^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^0. \quad (18)$$

Next, we sequentially solve the deterministic homogenization problem for the specific time t influencing the input variables basic moments given by the equations (8,12) around the mean values of those parameters to determine the coefficients $A_i^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$, $i=1, \dots, n$; it is apparent that they need to vary together with time parameter $A_i^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = A_i^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}(t)$, $i=1, \dots, n$. So that, the following system of equations is formed:

$$\begin{cases} A_1^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_1^{n-1} + A_2^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_1^{n-2} + \dots + A_n^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_1^0 = C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta(1)}^{(eff)} \\ A_1^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_2^{n-1} + A_2^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_2^{n-2} + \dots + A_n^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_2^0 = C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta(2)}^{(eff)} \\ \dots \\ A_1^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_n^{n-1} + A_2^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_n^{n-2} + \dots + A_n^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b_n^0 = C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta(n)}^{(eff)} \end{cases}, \quad (19)$$

where the coefficients $C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta(i)}^{(eff)}$ for $i=1, \dots, n$ denote the approximated components of the effective elasticity tensor values presented in ascending order of the arguments b_i . The unique solution for this system makes it possible calculation of up to n th order ordinary derivatives of the homogenized elasticity tensor with respect to the parameter b at the given b_0 as

- 1st order derivative

$$\frac{\partial C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(eff)}}{\partial b} = (n-1)A_1^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^{n-2} + (n-2)A_2^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^{n-3} + \dots + A_{n-1}^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, \quad (20)$$

- 2nd order derivative

$$\frac{\partial^2 C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(eff)}}{\partial b^2} = (n-1)(n-2)A_1^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^{n-3} + (n-2)(n-3)A_2^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^{n-4} + \dots + A_{n-2}^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, \quad (21)$$

- k^{th} order derivative

$$\frac{\partial^k C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^{(eff)}}{\partial b^k} = \prod_{i=1}^k (n-i)A_1^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^{n-k} + \prod_{i=2}^k (n-i)A_2^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} b^{n-(k+1)} + \dots + A_{n-k}^{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}. \quad (22)$$

4. COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS

Let us consider for an illustration a composite with the square periodicity cell and unitary dimensions; the fiber has a round cross-section and the expected value of its initial radius is taken as $E[R]=0,40$. The elastic properties of the glass fiber and epoxy matrix are adopted as follows: the Young moduli $E_1=84$ GPa, $E_2=4.0$ GPa, the Poisson ratios are taken as $\nu_1=0.22$ for fiber and $\nu_2=0.34$ for the matrix and the FEM

discretization of the periodicity cell is given in Fig. 1 [3]; we postpone in this initial study the aging velocity in the Young moduli of the components for the brevity of a presentation. The first part of the computations was hybrid FEM-symbolic determination of the response functions of the homogenized tensor components with respect to the fiber radius ranging from 0,40 to 0,35 to be used in further stochastic perturbation-based analysis. The results of this procedure is given in Fig. 2 – a continuous line represents $C_{1111}^{(eff)}(R)$, the dash-dot line is responsible for the component $C_{1122}^{(eff)}(R)$, while the space-dash corresponds to $C_{1212}^{(eff)}(R)$. It is apparent that the polynomial interpolations obtained are smooth, continuous and monotonous within the given range of variability (the vertical axes are given in GPa).

Figure 1. Finite Element Method discretization of the RVE quarter.

Figure 2. The approximations of $C_{1111}^{(eff)}(R)$, $C_{1122}^{(eff)}(R)$, $C_{1212}^{(eff)}(R)$.

Having determined those functions it is possible to employ the relations (20-22) to determine the partial derivatives of those components with respect to the fibre radius and, next, to include them into the general relation (17) to recover the probabilistic moments of any order. Assuming finally the specific form of the aging process we can analyze the changes of i.e. the expect values of the effective elasticity tensor components with respect to the additional time changes in expectations and standard deviations of the fibre radius subjected to the stochastic decay. The results of further numerical experiments are presented in Fig. 3 for $C_{1111}^{(eff)}(R)$ (expectations at the left and the standard deviations at the right), in Fig. 4 for $C_{1122}^{(eff)}(R)$ (the same order as before)

and for $C_{1212}^{(eff)}(R)$ (expectations at the left and the variances at the right hand side). The variability range for the expected values corresponds to its decrease from initial value 0,40 to the final 0,35, while its coefficient of variation ranges from 0,0 to 0,25. Such a presentation assures the maximum generality of the analysis since the continuous spectrum of the aging processes is collected here and, furthermore, the aging interdependence on time remains undefined (to finally fit this time scale using the first two moments combination into the given level of an environment aggressive behaviour).

Figure 3. The expected values and standard deviations for the component $C_{1111}^{(eff)}(\omega; t)$.

Figure 4. The expected values and standard deviations for the component $C_{1122}^{(eff)}(\omega; t)$.

All the probabilistic moments given in Figs. 3-5 show the same tendencies – they decrease together with a decrease of both expectations and the coefficients of variations of the fibre radius (a maximum is obtained for the upper limits on those variables). Analyzing those figures one may notice that having even a linear decay in expectations for the simplest aging rule, the additional decay in standard deviations (or variances)

remains quadratic. Therefore, the grids given on the surfaces presented are not adequate to the specific aging mechanisms. Further, a decrease of the expected values for the fibre from 0,40 to 0,34 corresponds (for most of the engineering fibres) to the period of time from 50 to 100 years rather than the few years intervals only. The second important observation is that the expected values of all homogenized tensor components changes decrease more than 10 times from their initial values in the case of deterministic analysis (when the parameter is close to 0), while the analogous decrease for the maximum value of α is not so significant. Comparing the influence of the expected value of the fibre radius and its coefficient of variation (for the given variability intervals) it is clear that they are of almost the same importance in the case of final standard deviations (or variances); the coefficient of variation is essentially more important for the changes of the homogenized tensor components expectations than the relevant expected value of the fibre radius.

Figure 5. The expected values and the variances for the component $C_{1212}^{(eff)}(\omega; t)$.

The next computational analyses will allow for a more precise comparison of the aging process effects applied to various composite parameters like geometrical and, separately, material characteristics of the composite constituents. The methodology applied guarantees that the analysis shown above may be extended on the other types of composites, different constitutive relations as well as on the other aging stochastic rules.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

1. As one may noticed here, the generalized stochastic perturbation technique can be very efficient computational modeling tool not only for the engineering problems with random parameters or fields but also in the case of the stochastic processes. Now, the response function determination provided before only once for the random variables, is performed for various time moments belonging to the time domain of the considered process. Nevertheless, we still need the initial determination of the probabilistic moments for a given stochastic process, so that effectively we need very precise information (or the assumption) on the stochastic quantities to be taken into account.

2. This methodology may be successfully extended on various mechanical problems for composites, not only in the context of the homogenization method, where one or the whole group of the parameters is subjected to some stochastic variations. The basic minor point would be a determination of the discrete response functions from one degree of freedom to the other, which, especially in nonlinear problems, may be quite expensive (considering the computational time). The second issue would be the application of the problems with the other than the Gaussian random quantities – it would need some modifications of the perturbation-based formulas, where both even and odd order moments and coefficients would be applicable.

3. The separate and the very important problem is a continuation of the research on the stochastic aging models, somewhat in parallel to the theories known from the computational biology. Although it is possible to insert much more advanced models here including the random disasters acting accidentally on composite structures like airplanes for instance, one need to remember that they need to fit into some computational procedures to compute the additional reliability indices with the satisfactory accuracy.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to acknowledge the financial support of the research grant from the Polish Ministry of the Research and Higher Education, NN 519 386 636.

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